

BIG DATA ANALYTIC ENABLER FOR CAPACITY PLANNING

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ABSTRACT

Capacity planning in modern enterprises has become increasingly intricate due to the exponential growth of data volumes and the complexity of organizational structures. Traditional capacity planning methods often struggle to adapt to the dynamic and heterogeneous nature of contemporary data ecosystems. In response, this paper proposes the utilization of Big Data analytics as a transformative enabler for capacity planning processes.

This study presents a comprehensive review of existing literature, examining the role of Big Data analytics in enhancing capacity planning strategies across various industries. The review synthesizes insights from academic research, industry reports, and case studies to identify key themes, methodologies, and best practices.

The findings reveal that Big Data analytics offer unique capabilities that traditional approaches lack, including predictive modeling, simulative modeling, and scalability. By harnessing these capabilities, organizations can gain deeper insights into their infrastructure performance, demand patterns, and resource utilization, thus enabling proactive and data-driven decision-making in capacity planning.

Moreover, the article highlights the challenges and barriers associated with integrating Big Data analytics into capacity planning processes, such as data quality issues and skill gaps. Addressing these challenges requires a multidisciplinary approach that combines technological innovation with organizational readiness and strategic alignment.

In conclusion, this paper underscores the transformative potential of Big Data analytics as a catalyst for enhancing capacity planning practices. By leveraging advanced analytics techniques and embracing a culture of data-driven decision-making, we can optimize resource allocation through Kibana and the capacity planning enabler we developed, mitigate risks, and capitalize on emerging opportunities in today's dynamic business landscape.

Keywords: capacity planning, predictive module, simulation module, big data analytics enabler, resource utilization, use cases.

I. INTRODUCTION

Capacity planning is a critical process for organizations to ensure they have the right resources in place to meet current and future demands effectively. A capacity planning enabler refers to any tool, methodology, or technology that facilitates this process, enabling businesses to optimize their resource allocation and improve operational efficiency. These enablers come in various forms and serve different functions, but their goal is to help organizations make informed decisions about resource utilization, infrastructure investment, and performance optimization.

One key enabler of capacity planning is data analytics. By analyzing historical data on resource usage, demand patterns, and performance metrics, organizations can forecast future requirements more accurately. Advanced analytics techniques, such as predictive modeling and machine learning, allow for more sophisticated forecasting, considering various factors that may impact resource needs, such as seasonality, market trends, and business growth.

Another important enabler is technology infrastructure, including hardware and software systems that support resource management and allocation. Process automation is another critical enabler of capacity planning. By automating routine tasks such as data collec-

tion, analysis, and reporting, organizations can streamline the capacity planning process and reduce the risk of human error.

Collaboration tools and techniques also play a vital role in capacity planning. By facilitating communication and collaboration among different teams and departments involved in resource management, organizations can ensure that everyone has access to the information they need to make informed decisions.

Overall, capacity planning enablers are essential for organizations to effectively manage their resources and ensure they can meet current and future demands efficiently. By leveraging data analytics, technology infrastructure, process automation, and collaboration tools, organizations can optimize resource utilization, improve operational performance, and maintain a competitive edge in today's dynamic business environment.

Therefore, this paper aims to provide an analytic enabler with use cases of capacity planning. The specific objectives of the paper are:

- According to the expert, the number of devices that connect to the Internet will be approximately 50 billion by 2020. It is important to analyze data of those devices generated by their sensors.

- The analytic enabler contains multiple use cases for different scenarios such as simulation, predictive analytics, and monitoring analytics of the data on

Call, SMS, and Internet. The CDR data we used is from the telecommunication company Telecom Italia.

- The design of the use cases provides solutions for monitoring the calling, SMS, and internet traffic from the operator, to ensure that the level of traffic is not going to pass the capacity available from the operator, and predict or forecast the traffic; therefore, helping the operator to better planning to reduce cost and early detection of network capacity issues.

- The business value is to accurately predict future capacity requirements to minimize investment costs, avoid or eliminate the excess capacity to maximize ROI (Return on Investment), and prevent future network capacity issues that might happen.

A. Significance of the work

Providing an analytic enabler in the context of capacity planning offers several significant benefits that directly impact an organization's ability to efficiently allocate resources and optimize performance. This work provides an analytic enabler in the use case of capacity planning that is of significant research interest due to its potential; among others, to enhance, decision-making, improve forecasting accuracy, optimize resource utilization, mitigate risks, support strategic planning, and gain a competitive advantage in today dynamic business environment.

B. Limitations of the work

This paper is limited to designing an analytic enabler and implementing multiple use cases for different scenarios such as simulation, predictive analytics, and monitoring analytics of the CDR data, mainly, *Call, SMS, and Internet* attributes from the operator, to ensure that the level of traffic does not pass the capacity available from the operator. For the capacity planning, we focused on the monitoring module, simulation module and predictive module with a minor aspect of the descriptive module.

C. Delimitations of the work

In this part of the section, we give a brief overview of the structure and content of this paper, which is divided into 4 main sections. Section I "Introduction" covers the introduction of the research paper where we explain the statement of the problem, motivation, and the research significance, objectives, limitations, and delimitations of the work.

Section II titled "Literature Review" covers capacity planning. We showed how capacity planning enablers can be applied in the context of our research paper. We also explore existing analytics techniques used to address capacity planning. We conclude by discussing some of the limitations of the methods and techniques.

Section III, "Overview of the Analytic Enabler" covers the architecture of the analytic enabler focused on 3 parts: the ETL, the Function module, and the API and data repositories in the enabler. We explore the programming language and open-sourced applications used.

Section IV, titled "Use cases", presents the Prediction model with a detailed demonstration of how the prediction module works from extracting the original data to visualization. The simulation module is also

used to generate data in the same format as the original sample data, in the case of lacking data for analysis.

Section V "Results" presents the entire city of Milano into 10000 different cells for better visualization of the telecommunication traffic.

Section VI "Conclusions, recommendation, and perspectives" summarizes our research work, evaluates the developed enabler, and states recommendations for future works.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several study papers and books explored different aspects of big data analytics capacity planning enablers. Among others: Verma, S. and Chaudhary, S. (2017) "Big Data Analytics: A Boon to Business for Capacity Planning and Management" explores the transformative impact of big data analytics on enhancing capacity planning and management strategies in businesses, presented through insights from the 2017 International Conference on Next Generation Computing and Communication Technologies. [1].

Chen, M., Mao, S., and Liu, Y. (2014) provide a comprehensive overview of the landscape, challenges, and potential applications of big data, offering insights into its multifaceted aspects within mobile networks and applications. [2].

Big Data Analytics for Capacity Planning in Cloud Computing by Bhadani and Nandi delves into the crucial role of big data analytics in optimizing capacity planning strategies specifically tailored for the dynamic environment of cloud computing, as presented in the 2018 International Conference on Computing, Communication, and Networking Technologies [3].

Big Data Analytics in Supply Chain Management: A State-of-the-Art Literature Review, by Hasan, L. and Alam, K. (2018) offers a comprehensive examination of the current advancements, challenges, and potential applications of big data analytics within the realm of supply chain management [4].

Liu, X., Shen, H., and Luo, Y. demonstrate the integration of big data analytics into a demand-driven Material Requirements Planning (MRP) system, emphasizing its potential to enhance manufacturing efficiency and responsiveness [5].

Bhadani, S. and Nandi, S. also present an innovative methodology leveraging big data analytics to optimize load balancing and capacity planning strategies within cloud computing environments [6].

Hu, L., Cao, Z., and Xu, H. (2016) delineate an innovative approach employing big data analytics to optimize capacity planning in power grids, showcasing its potential for enhancing efficiency and reliability [7].

Li, Y. and Dong, Li. (2019) introduces an innovative model tailored for dynamic capacity planning within big data applications, addressing the evolving needs and challenges in optimizing resource allocation and performance [9].

Li, X. and Li, D. (2018) offer an extensive analysis of the applications, challenges, and advancements in utilizing big data analytics to enhance demand response strategies within smart grid systems [10].

Ejiabyi (2015) provides detailed instructions for the installation and setup of the ELK (Elasticsearch,

Logstash, Kibana) stack on Ubuntu 14, tailored for Ericsson Canada's internal use, aiming to facilitate big data analytics within their infrastructure [11]

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this section, we discuss methods and the overall architecture of the Analytic Enabler.

A. Overview of the proposed Architecture of our Analytic Enabler

The enabler is mostly focused on 3 parts: the ETL, the function module (descriptive, monitoring, and more), and the API. data repositories are also required in the enabler. As shown in Figure 1.1, the services interact with each other to extract the data, process the data, and then display the data on the interface. For the data repositories, our enabler uses Apache Hadoop distribution system and Hive to store the CDR, Hive is very similar to MySQL. The ETL (extract, transform, and load) is the part where users take unorganized or organized data and upload it to the function module. The data can be in any format, has no standard, can

have missing parts, is often not in order, and can be very messy. The ETL must be able to extract the data and be able to transform it into a format that our application can read, and then load into our program. In our case, we have designed our own Python script for ETL (or let us call it preprocessing) but also used open-sourced applications such as Open Refine. For Capacity Planning, we focus on the monitoring module, simulation module, and predictive module with a little bit of descriptive module, (descriptive module will be more in the first use case of Smart City). The descriptive module simply displays the data on the interface, the monitoring module builds on the existing descriptive module with real-time monitoring. The predictive module takes past data to predict the future or forecasting. The simulation module generates new CDR in the case that we lack more data for analysis. The API is mostly HTML-based, and some use cases are displayed on Google Maps. The open-source application ELK is also used to display simulation and prediction results.

ANALYTIC ENABLER ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1. Analytic Enabler Architecture

B. Materials. The programming language and applications used.

In this Capacity Planning use case, many open-sourced applications, our own Python script, HTML and JavaScript-based web interface, and Database were used. It is listed below:

- Open Refine
- ELK (elasticsearch, logstash, and kibana)

- Python script
- HTML and JavaScript web page with the implementation of Google Map
- Web browser Firefox version 43.0.1 (chrome and EE might not work)
- Hadoop distribution system and Hive Database.

Fig. 2. Applications and languages used.

Open Refine is an open-sourced application for data wrangling used in our ETL. It is used for extracting needed data from an unstructured data format, and it can easily remove the empty or missing places by replacing them with suitable numbers. Then it can be exported into multiple file formats. It is user-friendly and very easy to download with one click of a button and ready to be used in no time. The ELK (Elasticsearch, Logstash, and Kibana) is one complete, complex, and complicated application that can be used for data extraction, data processing, and displaying data in all kind of tables, circles or graph. In our case, it is used purely for displaying the results of the simulation and prediction program.

Deeply it takes a lot of time to learn, install, and configure the ELK. The most part of the analytic enabler is written in Python, because Python is very easy

for organizing, managing, extracting, and modifying big data. HTML and JavaScript are the easiest ways for us to create an interface with the implementation of Google Maps. In this use case, most data are not stored in Hive (unlike the Smart City use case), because it is simply faster and easier to directly download the CDR and load it into our enabler.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, we will discuss the results of our findings based on the Analytic Enabler architecture discussed in Section III.

A. Design and Analysis

Target area and data under experiment. Raw data is collected from the city of Milano, which can be represented as a large area of 100 squares side (10K squares in sum).

Fig. 3. Applications and languages used.

We focus on studying the interaction of cells with ID=9999. All cells are summarized in a JSON file, and each cell is defined by its type, the cell ID, and the cell EPSG attributes such as geometry type and coordinates. The above figure shows the plaza of Milano under experiment and the target cell 9999 (WGS84 - EPSG:4326) in the city on Google Maps.

See more details in the [Description tab](#)

Filename	Size	Created	Modified	Get it
december/full.zip	2.5 GB	Fri 17 Jan 2014 12:13	Fri 17 Jan 2014 12:13	Download
november/full.zip	2.5 GB	Fri 17 Jan 2014 12:13	Fri 17 Jan 2014 12:13	Download
sms-call-internet-mi-2013-11-01.zip	79.9 MB	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Download
sms-call-internet-mi-2013-11-02.zip	78.4 MB	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Download
sms-call-internet-mi-2013-11-03.zip	77.0 MB	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Download
sms-call-internet-mi-2013-11-04.zip	87.9 MB	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Download
sms-call-internet-mi-2013-11-05.zip	89.8 MB	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Download
sms-call-internet-mi-2013-11-06.zip	90.1 MB	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Download
sms-call-internet-mi-2013-11-07.zip	89.9 MB	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Download
sms-call-internet-mi-2013-11-08.zip	90.9 MB	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Download
sms-call-internet-mi-2013-11-09.zip	82.3 MB	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Download
sms-call-internet-mi-2013-11-10.zip	77.8 MB	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Download
sms-call-internet-mi-2013-11-11.zip	86.5 MB	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Fri 10 Jan 2014 21:49	Download

Fig. 4. Outgoing density details from 9999 to destinations

B. Data under Exploration and preliminary analysis

Here is the dataset list downloaded for our study. The complete dataset of CDR for 2 months. For our preliminary analysis, we extract only datasets of the attributes of Cell 9999. But, for further analysis, such as prediction, we will need more than a cell or one-day observation.

We need specifically to use November 1st through November 5th. In general, any day datasets can be downloaded or explored, but the minimum of files needed is two, otherwise, the prediction result is the same as the original file, because we use Random Forest to predict, which will be covered in detail later.

Preliminary analysis is done by clustering the traffic patterns between the targeted cell and the remaining destinations. This data is the result of SMS & Call measurements for the December 31st, 2013, and January 01st, 2014 on Cell 9999 (Code 39 for Italy).

Let us remain that, to achieve this, the whole raw data related to cell 9999, has been extracted. Then, figure 3 shows the traffic details between cell 9999 and other destinations identified here, by their Codes. Codes 39, 0 & 49, 33, 48, 41, 221, 32, 40, 46, 44, 20, and 375, represent Calls and SMS interaction intensities with Italy, Germany, France, Poland, Switzerland, Senegal, Belgium, Romania, Sweden, United Kingdom, Egypt, and Belarus.

Fig. 3. Outgoing density details from 9999 to destinations [3]

Local calls are major. The main attributions explored here are square_ID, time_interval, and country_code, which describe the zonal coverage of a set of antennas versus city geographical areas. SMS_In,Out,

Call_In,Out, and Internet Traffic densities represent the distribution of main patterns, which provide correlation to the geography for deriving population constituency and habits.

Fig. 4. Incoming density details from destinations to 9999 [4]

Figure 4 shows the traffic details from destinations to cell 9999, by codes. The density of data exchanged has been also examined, in the same way as SMS_In and Call_In. As shown here, as for the Calls and SMS, major data is exchanged in the cell 9999.

B. Use cases Implementation: Results and Discussion

Prediction Module. The prediction module is used for forecasting to prevent future capacity issues and provide better information in the operator’s planning strategy. In this case, the data of the Internet traffic from the city of Milan are used to predict future traffic. First, we need to preprocess the selected file, because

the file contains data of 10000 cells in the Milano grid, learn how this CDR works first.

In our approved concept, we want to predict one cell, not 10000 cells. Therefore, we choose cell 1 to country 39, remembering that the interaction is always between 2 objects (it can be either cell or country, in this case, it is a country). The script **preprocessing.py** takes data of cell 1 to country 39; it will change the .txt file into .csv and replace all the empty data with 0. And write it into another file name (for example, 11-06.txt → 11-06.csv). Another python script **predict_preprocessing.py** will merge all 4 files and put it into one file under the name **predict_result.csv**. The following figure shows such a prediction.

Fig. 5. Prediction Module results [5]

Here, is a detailed demonstration of how the prediction module works from extracting the original data to the visualization. We needed a training dataset which is our 11-01 to 11-04 merged into one file **predict_preprocessing.csv**, then we need a test dataset which is the data to be predicted in the figure; then we produce the predicted result.

Training dataset + test dataset = predicted result

The function above is just a metaphor, not an actual addition. Our training dataset contains 9 columns right now, **time_length**, cell number (always 1),

timestamp, countrycode (always 39), **call_in**, **call_out**, **sms_in**, **sms_out**, and Internet attributes.

We use Open Refine to perform file format compatibility into the same format as in the training dataset of Figure 5. Kibana can be used for better results. Because, before using Kibana, we only have the result file which is only one column of Interact strength. When we displayed it on Kibana, we only saw one graph, but what if we want to compare it with the original data? We can merge as many files as we want, depending on how we wish to display the result. To achieve this, we combine Kibana with Elasticsearch and Logstash.

Fig. 6. Visualization of predicted results on Kibana [6]

Simulation Module. The simulation module is used to generate data in the same format as the original sample, in the case of lacking data for analysis, it can also add extra variables or increase the value of the variable if needed. The focus is to allow a no-programmer to be able to run and do a small demo of the application, for a full-detail demonstration. This detail demonstration shows how this application works from scratch to the generation of simulation data.

The process is similar to the section from the prediction module since both modules use the same data for the process. But instead of downloading a few files of individual days, we need to download at least 28 files (28 days of data), because the simulation needs an input of one month's data (28 for this case). Then, we extracted and uploaded the 28 files on the Python server (our Ubuntu server).

This module is not just about one click of a button and the job is done. The first task is to preprocess the large amount of data, therefore the **preprocessing.py** file was modified to be able to select the needed data, replace all the empty values by 0, and convert a .tsv file into a .csv. This Python script is different from the one of the prediction module, similar but slightly enhanced for this purpose of the simulation.

After the preprocessing of all 28 files, we need to merge all of 28 .csv files into one file for simplicity in uploading into the server. That is through the merge script **merge_28to1.py**. The resulting file is saved under **dec2015.csv** which is taken by the Python script

simulator4.py as an input to start reading it, first identifying the number of columns in the .csv file; therefore, it knows the number of columns that need to be simulated.

It stores the entire data of dec2015.csv into a multidimensional list, then separates them into 28 sub-lists, each list represents one day. Here introduce our **pattern recognition** process. The timestamp pattern recognition was not complete. Therefore, we assure the second column is always the timestamp and it has been hardcoded. For **float** number which represents most important data in CDR (Call, SMS, Internet), if the process detects float number, then it will be output as a float number.

For a more realistic data simulation, the first day of input file will generates the first day of the output file, for example, Dec 1 will be used to simulate Jan 1.

To be even more specific, the same day (input and output), the hour of the day will be used for generating the same hour of the output file. For example, the data between 5 pm to 6 pm from Dec 1 will be used to simulate the data between 5 pm to 6 pm on Jan 1.

Therefore, the simulation data is as similar as the original data as possible. For our study, we need the simulation data to grow or increase over time, therefore the percentage increase was implemented to perform this task. The float number (important variable) of the output or result file will have an increase of the percentage entered by the user on the interface. The next figure shows the Multivariable graph on Kibana.

Fig. 7. Multivariable graph on Kibana [7]

Milano Grid. Milano Grid is used to present the entire city of Milano into 10000 different cells for better visualization of the telecommunication traffic. We

focus on a detailed demonstration of how this application works from downloading, preprocessing, and displaying the data on the API.

Fig. 8. Milan Grid display Internet traffic [8]

The color displays the level of the Internet traffic in the 10000 cells, for example, when Internet traffic is higher than 40, the color is red. When it is between 40 and 20, the color is yellow. And when it is below 20, the color is green. It can be easily modified with a change of number in the HTML code. The grid loops every 5 sec, to display the next 10 min. for example, when it starts, it displays the Internet traffic at 7:00 am, then after the first loop, it displays traffic at 7:10 am, and it goes on and on.

This time the user needs to download something different, the user needs the JSON file that contains all the coordination of the Milano Grid. After downloading **milano-grid.zip**, we extract it and put it on the server. Now back to the same process from the simulation and

prediction, we needed to download one day of data (any day is fine).

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper covers the IoT Big Data Analytic Enabler and its main components, from overview, implementation instructions, and a detailed demonstration of the different use cases.

Section II provided a Literature Review with several works achieved on areas, such as big data Analytics, Elastic stack, and existing enablers.

Section III is an overview of the architecture of the Analytic Enabler and the open-sourced applications and tools, programming language, and scripts used to build this environment for the enabler. We went through the prediction module for forecasting the growth and the future daily or monthly pattern of the

telecommunication traffic; its purpose is to help the operator having a better understanding of the network and to prevent future network problems.

The second part of the section focuses on the simulation module to generate data in the case of testing or different usages; the data from the real company are usually hard to get and the application often needs a large quantity of the data to test.

Section IV covers use cases that were built for the analytic enabler. Among others, we detailly demonstrated the working function of both Predictive and Simulation modules. how our enabler displays. The latest use case is focused on the Milano Grid which displays and monitors all the Internet traffic in the city of Milano. For this purpose, Milano was divided into 10000 cells for easy presentation.

In conclusion, the development of this analytic enabler hopefully can be useful for future developers in IoT-big data analytics. Thus, the journey towards leveraging Big Data Analytics as a capacity planning enabler requires a holistic approach that encompasses technological innovation, organizational readiness, and strategic alignment. By embracing a culture of data-driven decision-making and continuously evolving their capacity planning practices, organizations can position themselves for sustained growth and competitive advantage in today's digital economy.

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